

BOOSTING THE QUALITY OF INSTRUCTOR SERVICES THROUGH HUMAN AND ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS

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Abstract

This study aims to produce a strategy to improve the quality of instructor services by strengthening the variables of Personality, Interpersonal Communication, and Organizational Support as independent variables and the variable of Job Satisfaction as an intervening variable. A population of 462 resulted in 215 samples taken by proportional random sampling at 12 Main Branch Offices (KCU) of CIMB Niaga in Jakarta. This study used a survey method with a path analysis approach and SITOREM analysis. The results of this study can be concluded: 1) There is a significant positive direct influence between personality, interpersonal communication, organizational support, and job satisfaction on the quality of instructor services; There is a significant positive direct influence between personality, interpersonal communication, organizational support on job satisfaction; There is a significant positive indirect influence between personality, interpersonal communication, and organizational support on the quality of instructor services through job satisfaction. Job satisfaction cannot function as an intervening variable between personality, interpersonal communication, and organizational support on the quality of instructor services. The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the indicators that are still weak and need to be improved are: 1. Providing views, ideas, 2. concepts for organizational progress, 3. Generosity, 4. Opportunities for job promotion, 5. Coworkers, 6. Working conditions, 7. Working conditions, 8. Support from superiors, 9. Organization, 10. Deep attention to customer needs, 11. Quality of facilities, infrastructure, and service facilities, and 12. Sincerity, self-confidence, and skills in serving.

Keywords: Instructor Service Quality, Personality, Interpersonal Communication, Organizational Support, Job Satisfaction and SITOREM.

INTRODUCTION

The digital era is driving many changes, especially in education, where the education sector has already adopted disruptive technologies such as Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT) in its services. Currently, almost all organizations emphasize quality, with the strong drive of business organizations to achieve and maintain quality starting to be adopted by public organizations. Improving quality brings public

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organizations increased productivity and reduced costs. Education is a common phenomenon in every aspect of societal life, but the differences in philosophy and worldview adopted by each nation or society, and even individuals, lead to variations in the implementation of educational activities. Education, besides being universal, is also national in nature, and its national characteristics will color the implementation of education in that nation. For the sustainability of the process in education, a good governance system is required. The implementation of good governance is expected to offer a new paradigm in the world of education. Experience proves that efforts to improve the quality of education are not as simple and easy as imagined. Many aspects of education need to be reorganized to create a conducive climate for efforts to improve the quality of education.

According to Banglims (2015), a trainer is a coach who acquires knowledge, tests it, and then combines the results with several supplementary elements (which can be reduced or added) to form an effective and practical learning method. This enables training participants to absorb the knowledge applicatively and perform it exactly as demonstrated or directed by the trainer. The goal is Knowledge and Application. From the definitions above, it can be concluded that Training of Trainers (TOT) is a special training for trainers (and those interested in becoming trainers) that teaches techniques on how to deliver material engagingly to the audience.

The quality of human resources will greatly depend on the implementation of the training conducted. The success of a training implementation is measured by the extent to which the training results are transferred by the trainees in the workplace (transfer of training). Thus, the satisfaction of the training participants will greatly determine the transfer of training. In recent years, empirical support has been found for the relationship between the quality of service received and business performance (Athanasopoulos, et. al., 2001), which may be difficult to replicate. As a result, official instruments to measure consumer perceptions of the services provided are very important, especially because they can serve as evidence of consumer evaluations of service quality that lead to satisfaction or dissatisfaction. This is then linked to repurchase power, loyalty, and the desire to maintain a long-term relationship with the service provider.

CIMB Niaga believes that every employee has the same opportunity to advance and develop according to their potential, expertise, and available opportunities. Therefore, the development of Human Resource competencies at CIMB Niaga is carried out using an integrated approach designed with consideration of employee needs, organizational needs, and business objectives. This is regulated in the Employee Learning Implementation Policy No. A.07.05 and the CIMB Niaga employee code of ethics and conduct. CIMB Niaga, through the Human Resources Directorate (HRD), continuously conducts ongoing development and improvement. The development program is structured with consideration of effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and the learning objectives to be achieved. CIMB Niaga's focus in the development of educational and training programs for employees is: a). an integrated learning approach to support business needs and goals; b). Behavioral development; c). Managerial and leadership skills; and d). Functional abilities and specialized methods. CIMB Niaga has disclosed its policies

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and activities in employee training and development annually, which can be seen in the Bank's Annual Report and Sustainability Report.

Quality services will provide satisfaction to the training participants. The quality of instructor services is indicated by the motivation of training participants to share their satisfaction with academic services with others. Satisfaction according to Tjiptono (2017) states that satisfaction or dissatisfaction is the customer's response to the evaluation of the discrepancy/disconfirmation felt between previous expectations and the actual performance of the product experienced after its use. The level of instructor service quality in educational services can be determined by comparing the expectations with the reality experienced by the trainees. The quality of instructor services will be achieved if there is alignment between the services provided to the training participants. As stated by Tulak and Yelsi (2018), the quality of instructor services will be seen from the alignment between expectations and the performance of the services received. Starting from the basic concept of customer satisfaction, higher education institutions are essentially service industries that provide educational services to satisfy their customers. According to Tilaar (2002), training institutions today are faced with demands for quality and accountability for the educational services they provide, so quality services must be delivered to satisfy their customers.

The research conducted by Fan (2020) attempts to explore the factors influencing training effectiveness from the employees' perspective. To achieve this goal, the research used a quantitative data collection method, and data were collected from a small portion of employees working at the Chinese company Suning.com. In conclusion, less than half of Suning.com employees felt that the training provided by the company was beneficial. Several very important factors influence how effective training is. Many employees say that they do not receive an analysis of what they need for training, and the results of the training itself do not match the work they are currently doing. An additional 40% of the surveyed individuals stated that the necessary learning materials were not provided during the training process. The training schedule affects its effectiveness. According to the respondents, the training was conducted outside of regular working hours and the time provided was insufficient. Finally, some people in the company said that the management or teachers did not check how well the training worked after it was completed. These factors hinder effective training at Suning.com from the employees' perspective.

The results of the research by Shen and Tang (2021), titled: How does training improve customer service quality? The role of training transfer and job satisfaction. This study explores the role of training transfer and job satisfaction in the relationship between training and customer service quality. Data for this research were collected from employees and their supervisors in ten business organizations in Southern China. Data was collected from 230 employees and their supervisors and analyzed using structural equation modeling. The research results indicate that training indirectly affects customer service quality through the mediation of training transfer and job satisfaction. Training, directly and indirectly, affects training transfer through the mediation of job satisfaction,

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which in turn partially mediates the relationship between training transfer and customer service quality. Furthermore, perceived organizational support (POS) moderates the relationship between training and training transfer. This study extends social exchange theory, reciprocity norms, and goal-setting theory. These results show that high POS enhances the training effect on training transfer. The fully standardized structural coefficients for the theoretical model. The research concludes that Training and Job Satisfaction have a significant impact on service quality.

The research by Lee and Chen (2021) entitled: The Relationship between Employee Commitment and Job Attitude and Its Effect on Service Quality in the Tourism Industry. The main objective of this research is to analyze the relationship between employee commitment and job attitude in the tourism industry and its impact on service quality. Out of the 450 selected participants, 237 (52.6%) responded by filling out the questionnaire. This research study attempts to explain various theories related to employee commitment and work attitudes. Primary data for the research were obtained through questionnaires, using structured questions to explain the main objectives. This study uses a cross-sectional research design to meet its objectives. The results show a relationship between affective commitment and work attitude and a strong relationship between normative commitment and work attitude. In addition, there is a strong relationship between continuous commitment and work attitude. There is also a significant relationship between organizational commitment and work attitude.

Therefore, the training organizers need to evaluate the service factors that influence consumer satisfaction levels to improve service quality and provide a unique level of satisfaction to their consumers, namely the training participants. With the satisfaction of training participants towards the service, consumer loyalty to the organization will emerge, so consumers/society should be positioned as the primary focus to be satisfied in every planning and activity carried out.

LITERATURE REVIEW**Instructor Service Quality**

Service quality is the level of excellence provided by a service provider to consumers/customers or service recipients. The purpose of service quality is to meet or even exceed customer expectations. One way to improve employee competence is to take training. This is done so that employees have the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that are qualified to achieve the organization's vision. For participants to be able to transfer knowledge well from the training, the quality of the training implementation service must also be good, so that learning objectives can be achieved. With the achievement of the quality of training implementation services, it is hoped that it can increase human resource development.

Service quality is a comparison between the quality received, after receiving the service, with the expected quality, service quality indicators are as follows: reliability, namely consistency in providing services, responsiveness, namely responsiveness in providing services, assurance, namely guarantees of service quality, empathy, namely

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careful attention to customer needs, and tangibles, facilities, infrastructure and service facilities provided (Kotler, 2000).

Service quality is the customer's perception of the difference between the services received compared to the expected service. The indicators of service quality are as follows: reliability, namely accuracy and consistency in service, responsiveness, namely the willingness and speed of service, assurance, namely sincerity, self-confidence and skills in serving, empathy, namely deep attention to customer needs/problems, and tangibles, namely the quality of service facilities, infrastructure and facilities (Baines, Fill, & Page, 2011).

Service quality is a result that must be achieved and carried out with action. Service quality indicators are as follows: Tangible is a service that can be seen, smelled, and touched, Reliability is a dimension that measures the reliability of a company in providing services to its customers, Responsiveness is customer expectations regarding the speed of service that are almost certain to change with an upward trend over time, Assurance is a quality related to the company's ability and the behavior of front-line staff in instilling trust and confidence in its customers, and Empathy, namely attention to customer needs/desires (Supranto, 2005). According to Alwi, M and Hermawan, A (2023) Service quality is a form of consumer assessment of the level of service received with the level of service expected. The trust of the community using educational services is closely related to the quality of service of their school organization. The level of trust is built through the relationship between the services of educators in this case teachers and their students. The quality of teacher service is related to trust which essentially provides the best service to students, parents, and the surrounding community. The indicators of service quality are as follows: 1) reliability, namely accuracy and consistency in service, 2) responsiveness, namely the willingness and speed of service, 3) assurance, namely sincerity, self-confidence, and skills in serving, 4) empathy, namely deep attention to customer needs/problems, and 5) tangibles, namely the quality of facilities, infrastructure, and service facilities. Rusnadi, S. Hermawan, A. and Indrati, B., (2023) describe that service quality is the customer's perception of the comparison between the fulfillment of needs and desires, as well as the accuracy of delivery in balancing customer expectations which are closely related to the quality of products, services, and human resources. The indicators of service quality are as follows: 1) the ability to provide services according to promises accurately and reliably, 2) delivery of clear information (responsiveness), 3) trust in the institution (assurance), 4) trying to understand consumer desires (empathy), and 5) appearance and ability of the institution's physical facilities and infrastructure (tangibles). From the explanation of the theories above, it can be synthesized (concept definition) that service quality is the customer's perception of the comparison between the quality received (perceived quality) by the customer, after receiving the service, with the expected quality, with the service quality indicators as follows:

- a. Accuracy and consistency in service (reliability).
- b. Willingness and speed of service (responsiveness).

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- c. Sincerity, self-confidence, and skills in serving (assurance).
- d. Deep attention to customer needs/problems (empathy).
- e. Quality of facilities, infrastructure, and service facilities (tangibles).

Personality

Knowledge of personality helps in understanding others. It facilitates better communication, the development of stronger relationships, and reduces interpersonal conflict. Knowing one's personality can help one to recognize oneself, overcome weaknesses, and utilize strengths. According to Daft (2016) Personality is a set of characteristics that underlie relatively stable behavioral patterns in response to ideas, objects, or people in the environment managers who appreciate the differences in their employees' personalities have insight into the types of leadership behaviors that are most influential. Personality indicators are as follows: 1) extroversion; someone who is friendly, sociable, assertive, and comfortable with interpersonal relationships, 2) agreeableness; someone who can get along with others by being kind, likable, cooperative, forgiving, understanding, and trusting, 3) conscientiousness; someone who focuses on several goals, so that they behave in a responsible, reliable, persistent, and achievement-oriented manner, 4) emotional stability; the degree to which a person is calm, enthusiastic, and confident, not tense, depressed, moody, or insecure, and 5) openness to experience; someone who has a variety of interests and is imaginative, creative, artistically sensitive, and willing to consider new ideas. Luthans, F (2017) describes that personality is how people influence others and how they understand and view themselves, as well as how their inner and outer character measurement patterns measure traits and interactions between humans. The indicators of personality are as follows: physical condition, character, and individual maturation process. According to Ryckman, R.M. (2018) Personality is a set of dynamic and organized characteristics possessed by a person that uniquely influences their cognition, motivation, and behavior in various situations. Personality indicators are as follows: Attitude, Feelings, Expression, and Temperament.

Alwisol (2017) Explains that personality is behavior that is displayed in the social environment, the impression of oneself that is desired so that it can be captured by the social environment. Personality indicators are as follows: biological heritage, physical environment, culture, group life, and a person's typical experiences. According to Hermawan, A. Indrati, B. Susanti, E (2023) personality is a tendency in a person to explain the characteristics of their behavioral patterns that are consistent with their indicators, namely: 1) meticulous nature, 2) extrovert nature, 3) agreeable nature, 4) neurotic nature, and 5) openness to experience.

From the explanation of the theories above, it can be synthesized (concept definition) that Personality is a distinctive characteristic that is inherent and relatively stable in a person in the ways of feeling, thinking, and emotions that guide behavior and interaction in the environment. The personality indicators are as follows:

- a. Conscientiousness, namely the nature of being careful, the tendency to be responsible, reliable, and neat and orderly.

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- b. Friendliness, namely being sociable, kind, cooperative, sympathetic, helpful, warm, pleasant, polite, empathetic forgiving, warm, understanding, caring, can trust others, easy to get along with, and trustworthy).
- c. Emotional Stability is the tendency and ability to handle pressure or stress by remaining calm, not easily anxious, having a strong personality, focused and confident)
- d. Openness is characterized by having broad and imaginative interests, always curious, creative, complex, complicated, refined, polite, artistic, sensitive, interested, and willing to consider new ideas).
- e. Assertive Tendency is being firm and comfortable in dealing with others, passionate, brave, and dominant).

Interpersonal Communication

Interpersonal communication plays a role in changing and developing each other. These changes are through interaction in communication, giving each other inspiration, enthusiasm, and encouragement so that they influence a person's thoughts, feelings, and attitudes according to the topics being studied together. Interpersonal communication is an important foundation in building healthy and strong relationships. This involves the exchange of information and understanding between two or more individuals. Along with the development of technology, the ability to communicate effectively is increasingly important for the success of personal relationships.

DeVito, (2016) defines interpersonal communication as communication that takes place between two or more people who have a stable and clear relationship. Several aspects must be considered by the actors of interpersonal communication, namely: a) Openness, namely the ability to eliminate closed attitudes towards input from others and open up to others, and acknowledge the feelings and thoughts expressed are their own and are responsible for them; b) Empathy, namely the ability to put oneself in the position or role of another person. The ability to be able to understand what is felt and thought from the perspective of others emotionally and intellectually, namely; c) Supportive attitude, namely an attitude that is the opposite of a defensive attitude. Defensive people tend to protect themselves more from threats in communication situations. Creating a supportive atmosphere can be done by using non-verbal cues. In a supportive attitude, a person is open-minded, willing to listen to opposing views, and willing to change opinions and beliefs if the situation requires; d) Positive Attitude, namely interpersonal communication can respect oneself and others positively as well as those who have negative feelings towards themselves or others. Therefore, a positive attitude arises by starting from respect for oneself and others; e) Equality, namely interpersonal communication will take place effectively if the atmosphere is equal, namely, and there is a tacit recognition that both parties value, are useful, and have something important to contribute. Equality is the same thoughts, ideas, views, and ideas. Inequality, someone accepts others as they are without having to have certain conditions.

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According to Beebe, Beebe, and Redmond (2020) said that interpersonal communication is a form of transactional communication typical of humans that involves reciprocal influence, usually to manage relationships. The elements are as follows: a) source, the initiator of thoughts or emotions, who puts them into a code that can be understood by the recipient; b) encode, to translate ideas, feelings, and thoughts into code; c) decode, interpret ideas, feelings, and thoughts that have been translated into code; d) message, written, spoken, and unspoken elements of communication that people give meaning to; e) channel, the path through which the message is sent; f) receiver, the person who decodes the message and tries to understand what has been encoded by the source; g) noise, anything external (physiological) or internal (psychological) that interferes with the accurate reception of the message; h) feedback, response to a message. Interpersonal communication is an interaction characterized by the qualities of uniqueness, irreplaceability, interdependence, disclosure, and intrinsic reward. Its characteristics are as follows:

a) Transactional; b) intentional or unintentional; c) has a content and a relational dimension; d) irreversible, e. unrepeatable (Siregar and Hermawan (2023).

According to Hermawan, Ghozali, and Sayuti (2023), Interpersonal communication is an activity of sending and receiving Messages reciprocally carried out by individuals who have close relationships to achieve desired goals in an organization with indicators: 1) openness, 2) equality, 3) empathy, 4) positive attitude and 5) mutual support. From the explanation of the theories above, it can be synthesized (concept definition) that Interpersonal Communication is an activity of sending and receiving messages reciprocally carried out by individuals who have close relationships through verbal and non-verbal interactions to achieve organizational goals. The indicators of interpersonal communication are as follows: a. Openness to receive input from others

- b. Ability to understand others
- c. Providing support to others
- d. Being positive towards yourself and others
- e. Providing views, ideas, and ideas for the progress of the organization
- f. Ability to interpret every word, sentence, information, and behavior of others.

Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support is important because organizational members are more effective at work when they receive appreciation. The more organizational members receive praise or recognition for what they do, the more likely they are to respond favorably to management changes and organizational needs. If organizational members feel positive about how they are treated in an organization, or how fairly they are compensated for their work, they may be more willing to support the organization during management changes, marketing challenges, and shifts in systems. Loyalty within an organization can help a business survive challenging circumstances.

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Robbins and Judge (2016) describe organizational support as the degree to which employees believe the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being, with the following indicators: (1) Fair appreciation of employee contributions, (2) Caring about their well-being, and (3) Supportive supervision. According to Nwanzu (2017), the organization is the degree to which employees believe the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. Indicators of organizational support are the organization values employee contributions, and the organization cares about employee wellbeing. Meanwhile, Langton and Robbins (2017) Perception of organizational support is the extent to which employees believe that their employers value their contributions to the organization and care about employee welfare. The indicators of organizational support are appreciating employee contributions to the organization and caring about employee welfare.

According to Rusnadi and Hermawan (2023), Organizational support is the level of employee confidence in the workplace organization that provides justice, values contributions, pays attention to welfare, recognizes employee values, and guarantees working conditions for employees. The indicators of Organizational Support are as follows: 1) providing justice, 2) leadership support, 3) rewards from the organization, and 4) working conditions. From the explanation of the theories above, it can be synthesized (concept definition) that Organizational support is the level of belief of organizational members in the workplace organization that provides justice, values contributions, pays attention to welfare, recognizes the values of organizational members, and guarantees working conditions for members of the organization. The indicators of organizational support are as follows: a. providing justice

- b. Leadership support
- c. Rewards from the organization
- d. Working conditions

Job Satisfaction

In general, organizations want their employees to feel happy in the work environment. So that employees are Comfortable, and loyal and do not leave their organization. From the employee's perspective, it can be assumed that this sense of happiness has a fairly good impact. Job satisfaction is a form of attitude of satisfaction and happiness with their current job. This sense of satisfaction is obtained because the company can meet employee needs well, such as achieving work goals, work environment dynamics, and other aspects that support employees in working. This sense of satisfaction with work can be reflected through several changing attitudes such as high levels of morale, discipline, motivation, productivity, achievement and work performance.

Job satisfaction is a person's level of pleasure obtained through job assessment or work experience. Job satisfaction is also identified with an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves work. Job satisfaction is a reflection of what we have thought and felt about a job that has been done. For members of the organization, a sense of pleasure will be achieved if the work that is done seriously and with high responsibility has an impact

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on achieving organizational goals. This job satisfaction will be created if individuals get good work results, treatment, placement, and work atmosphere. In other words, job satisfaction will be achieved when individuals feel their needs are met through their work. True job satisfaction can be achieved by individuals when what they do has a direct impact on improving the organization. This can only be done if members of the organization have a strong attachment to their organization. Therefore, it is reasonable to suspect that there is a relationship between job satisfaction and engagement.

Cerci and Dumludag, D. (2019) explain that job satisfaction is a positive or pleasant emotional state resulting from an assessment of a person's work or work experience. With dimensions 1) job promotion prospects, 2) total salary, 3) relationship with superiors, 4) job security or guarantee, 5) workability based on initiative, 6) work conditions, and 7) length of service. Factors related to working conditions, academics, and income affect job satisfaction. According to Ratih, and Sintaasih (2017), job satisfaction refers to an individual's total attitude towards their work. With dimensions 1). The work itself, namely the extent to which the work is an interesting task, an opportunity to learn, and an opportunity to accept responsibility, 2). A proper reward is a recognition by giving something for the results of the work, 3). The work environment is a physical environment that is safe, comfortable, clean, and has a minimum level of disturbance, 4). Coworkers, namely the extent to which co-workers are technically proficient and socially supportive, and 5). Pay namely the amount of financial remuneration received and the extent to which this is seen as fair compared to others in the organization. McShane and Glinow (2010) define Job Satisfaction as a person's evaluation of their work. With dimensions 1). Individual (the person), namely the worker himself, 2). Workplace (the workplace), namely the condition of the workplace, and 3). Country (the country) namely the condition of the country where the company is run. According to Gibson, Ivancevich, and Donnelly Jr (2006), Job satisfaction is an individual's attitude towards his work, which comes from his perception of his work. With dimensions; 1) pay, namely salary, wages, honorarium, and others, 2) job, namely work conditions, facilities, challenges, and job requirements, 3) promotion opportunities, namely promotion opportunities, career development, and status enhancement, 4) supervisor, namely superior supervision and superior-subordinate relationships, and 5) co-workers, namely co-workers, teamwork, and others. The higher the employee's assessment of the factors of his work, the higher the level of satisfaction in working.

From the explanation of the theories above, it can be synthesized (concept definition) that Job satisfaction is an individual's emotional condition that arises from an assessment of his work, or experience in his work. The empowerment indicators are as follows:

- a. Rewards, namely related to salary, wages, and honorarium.
- b. Work conditions, namely every job require certain skills.
- c. Job promotion opportunities, namely factors related to the presence or absence of opportunities to get career advancement while working.

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- d. Superior supervision, namely good supervision from superiors of a job.
- e. Co-workers, namely factors related to the relationship between employees and their superiors and with other employees.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at the CIMB Niaga Employee Education and Training Institute in Jakarta. The results of the research survey were analyzed using Path Analysis to analyze the causal relationship between variables and estimate the coefficients of several linear structural equations that represent the hypothesis of a causal relationship. In a linear structural equation, the influence of independent variables on dependent variables can be in the form of direct and indirect influences. The indirect influence of independent variables on dependent variables can be tested through intervening variables. The total influence of independent variables on the dependent variable is the sum of the direct influence and all indirect influences. SITOREM analysis is then used to strengthen the results of the Path Analysis in more detail on the research variable indicators, to find indicators that need to be immediately improved and maintained or developed. The priority indicators are research findings used to prepare the Action Plan.

Figure 1. Research Constellation

The population of this study was CIMB Niaga employees participating in employee training in Jakarta totaling 462 employees. The determination of the number of research samples in this quantitative stage used the proportional Random sampling technique based on the Taro Yamane Formula. The sample is the portion of the number and characteristics that represent and are owned by the population. In this study, the error rate and confidence level used were 5%. Based on the sample determination calculation technique, the number of samples

was determined to be 215 respondents. Then the number of samples was determined at each university that was the sample area by determining the proportion according to the number of Main Branch Offices (KCU) studied. Data analysis is one of the research processes carried out after all the necessary data has been completely collected to solve the problem being studied. The accuracy of conclusions is determined by the accuracy of the use of data analysis techniques, therefore data analysis techniques are carried out by researchers so that the results of their research are truly able to contribute to problem-solving and can be scientifically accounted for. The data analysis technique used in this quantitative study is to use descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Table 1. Summary of hypothesis testing results

No	Hypothesis	Path	Statistic Test	Decision	Conclusion
1.	Creativity (X1) towards Teacher Engagement (Y)	0.210	$H_0 : \beta y_1 \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta y_1 > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Direct Positive Impact
2.	Organizational Support (X2) towards Teacher Engagement (Y)	0.354	$H_0 : \beta y_2 \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta y_2 > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Direct Positive Impact
3.	Adversity Intelligence (X3) towards Teacher Engagement (Y)	0.173	$H_0 : \beta y_3 \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta y_3 > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Direct Positive Impact
4.	Achievement Motivation (X4) towards Teacher Engagement (Y)	0.194	$H_0 : \beta y_4 \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta y_4 > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Direct Positive Impact
5.	Creativity (X1) towards Achievement Motivation (X4)	0.236	$H_0 : \beta X_1 X_4 \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta X_1 X_4 > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Direct Positive Impact
6.	Organizational Support (X2) towards Achievement Motivation (X4)	0.238	$H_0 : \beta X_2 X_4 \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta X_2 X_4 > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Direct Positive Impact
7.	Adversity Intelligence (X3) towards Achievement Motivation (X4)	0.233	$H_0 : \beta X_3 X_4 \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta X_3 X_4 > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Direct Positive Impact

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8.	Creativity (X1) towards Teacher Engagement (Y) through Achievement Motivation (X4)	0.049	$H_0 : \beta_{14y} \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta_{14y} > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Positive Indirect Impact
9.	Organizational Support (X2) towards Teacher Engagement (Y) through Achievement Motivation (X4)	0.084	$H_0 : \beta_{24y} \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta_{24y} > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Positive Indirect Impact
10.	Adversity Intelligence (X3) towards Teacher Engagement (Y) through Achievement Motivation (X4)	0.040	$H_0 : \beta_{34y} \leq 0$ $H_1 : \beta_{34y} > 0$	H_0 rejected H_1 accepted	Positive Indirect Impact

Table 2. Analysis of research variable indicators

No	Variable	Effect		Conclusion
		Direct	Indirect X4	
1.	Personality (X1)	0.210	0.049	Direct influence (0.210) > Indirect influence (0.049)
2.	Interpersonal Communication (X2)	0.354	0.084	Direct influence (0.354) > Indirect influence (0.084)
No	Variable	Effect Direct	Indirect X4	Conclusion
3.	Organizational Support (X3)	0.173	0.040	Direct influence (0.173) > Indirect influence (0.040)
4.	Job Satisfaction (X4)	0,194	-	-

Based on the value of direct influence and indirect influence on teacher engagement (Y), the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The value of the direct influence of personality (X1) on instructor service quality (Y) is greater than the value of the indirect influence of creativity (X1) on instructor service quality (Y) through job satisfaction (X4), so it can be concluded that job satisfaction (X4) does not function effectively as an intervening variable between personality (X1) and instructor service quality (Y).
- The value of the direct influence of interpersonal communication (X2) on instructor service quality (Y) is greater than the value of the indirect influence of interpersonal communication (X2) on instructor service quality

(Y) through job satisfaction (X4), so it can be concluded that job satisfaction (X4) does not function effectively as an intervening variable between interpersonal communication (X2) and instructor service quality (Y).

3. The value of the direct influence of organizational support (X3) on the quality of instructor services (Y) is smaller than the value of the indirect influence of organizational support (X3) on the quality of instructor services (Y) through job satisfaction (X4), so it can be concluded that job satisfaction (X4) does not function effectively as an intervening variable between organizational support (X3) and the quality of instructor services (Y). In the context of this study, in addition to using Path Analysis, it also uses SITOREM analysis.

Scientific Identification Theory to Conduct Operation Research in Education Management (SITOREM), is a scientific method used to identify variables (theories) to carry out "Operation Research" in the field of Educational Management (Hardhienata, 2017). SITOREM analysis is carried out by identifying and analyzing three things, namely: a) Identification of the strength of influence between the Independent Variable and the Dependent Variable; b) Analysis of the value of research results for each indicator of the research variable, and c) Analysis of the weight of each indicator of each research variable based on the criteria "Cost, Benefit, Urgency, and Importance. The results of the SITOREM analysis are as follows:

Table 3. Determination of SITOREM Analysis Results

PERSONALITY ($\beta_{y1} = 0,210$) (Rank.II)				
Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert		Indicator Value
1	Emotional Stability	1st	Emotional Stability (22.88%)	4.17
2	Open to social interaction	2nd	Open to social interaction (20.02%)	4.19
3	Open to new experiences	3rd	Open to new experiences (19.28%)	4.22
4	Generosity	4th	Conscientiousness (19.28%)	3.75
5	Conscientiousness	5th	Generosity (18.55%)	3.98

INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION ($\beta_{y2} = 0,354$) (Rank.I)				
Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert		Indicator Value
1	Openness to receive input from others	1st	Openness to receive input from others (17.72%)	4.27
2	Ability to understand others	2nd	Being positive towards yourself and others (17.72%)	4.02

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3	Providing support to others	3rd	Ability to interpret every word, sentence, information, and behavior of others. (16.46%)	4.05
INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION ($\beta_{y2} = 0,354$) (Rank.I)				
Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert		Indicator Value
4	Being positive towards yourself and others	4th	Providing views, ideas, and concepts for the advancement of the organization. (16.46%)	3.88
5	Providing views, ideas, and concepts for the advancement of the organization	5th	Ability to understand others (15.82%)	4.27
6	Ability to interpret every word, sentence, information, and behavior of others.	6th	Providing support to others. (15.82%)	4.18

ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT ($\beta_{y3} = 0,173$) (Rank.IV)				
Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert		Indicator Value
1	Fairness	1st	Job Conditions (26.85%)	3.90
2	Supervisor Support	2nd	Supervisor Support (25.00%)	3.99
3	Work Standards	3rd	Organizational Rewards (25.00%)	3.69
4	Job Conditions	4th	Fairness (23.15%)	4.23
JOB SATISFACTION ($\beta_{y4} = 0,194$) (Rank.III)				
Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert		Indicator Value
1	Rewards	1st	Promotion opportunities (22.16%)	3.37
2	Conditions of employment	2nd	Co-workers (20.00%)	3.64
3	Opportunities for promotion	3rd	Rewards (19.28%)	4.10
4	Superior supervision	4th	Superior supervision (19.28%)	4.05

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5	Co-workers	5th	Working conditions (19.28%)	3.92
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INSTRUCTOR SERVICE QUALITY (Y)				
Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert		Indicator Value
1	Accuracy and consistency in service	1st	Accuracy and consistency in service (20.59%)	4.35
2	Willingness and speed of service	2nd	Willingness and speed of service (19.87%)	4.09
3	Sincerity, self-confidence, and skills in serving	3rd	Deep attention to customer needs/problems (19.85%)	3.95
4	Deep attention to customer needs/problems	4th	Quality of service facilities, infrastructure, and facilities (19.85%)	3.57
5	Kualitas sarana, prasarana dan fasilitas layanan	5th	Kesungguhan, keyakinan diri dan ketrampilan dalam melayani (19.85%)	3.30

ANALYSIS RESULTS STORE			
Priority Order of Indicators to be strengthened		Indicators to be maintained	
1st	Providing views, ideas, and concepts for the advancement of the organization.	1	Openness to receive input from others

ANALYSIS RESULTS STORE			
Priority Order of Indicators to be strengthened		Indicators to be maintained	
2nd	Conscientiousness	2	Being positive towards yourself and others
3rd	Agreeableness	3	The ability to interpret every word, sentence, information, and behavior of others.
4th	Promotion opportunities	4	The ability to understand others
5th	Co-Workers	5	Providing support to others.
6th	Job	6	Emotional Stability
7th	Job Conditions	7	Open to social interaction (Extraversion)
8th	Supervisor Support	8	Open to new experiences

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9 th	Organizational Rewards	9	Rewards (pay)
10 th	Deep attention to customer needs/problems (Empathy)	10	Superior supervision
11 th	Quality of facilities, infrastructure, and service facilities (Tangibles)	11	Fairness (providing justice)
12 th	Sincerity, self-confidence, and skills in serving (Assurance)	12	Accuracy and consistency in service (Reliability)
		13	Willingness and speed of service (Responsiveness)

CONCLUSION

1. A strategy is produced to improve the quality of instructor services through the identification of the strength of influence between research variables. The strategy for improving the quality of instructor services is through strengthening personality variables, interpersonal communication, organizational support, and job satisfaction.

2. A way to strengthen research variables is produced. Some findings related to indicators in research variables need to be improved and some need to be maintained or developed.

3. An optimal solution is produced to improve teacher engagement, namely improving weak indicators and maintaining or developing good indicators. The indicators that need to be improved consist of: 1st providing views, ideas, and concepts for the advancement of the organization, 2nd conscientiousness, 3rd generosity, 4th job promotion opportunities, 5th coworkers, 6th job conditions, 7th job condition, 8th supervisor support, 9th organizational, 10th deep attention to customer needs/problems (empathy), 11th quality of facilities, infrastructure and service facilities (tangibles), and 12th sincerity, selfconfidence and skills in serving (assurance). Meanwhile, the indicators that are maintained and developed are: 1) openness to receive input from others, 2) being positive towards yourself and others, 3) ability to interpret every word, sentence, information, and behavior of others, 4) ability to understand others, 5) providing support to others, 6) emotional stability, 7) openness to social interaction (extraversion), 8) openness to new experiences, 9) rewards (pay), 10) supervisor supervision, 11) fairness (providing justice), 12) accuracy and consistency in service (reliability), and 13) willingness and speed of service (responsiveness).

Based on the results of the analysis, discussion of research results, and the proposed hypothesis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

a. There is a significant positive direct effect between personality (X1) on the quality of instructor service (Y) with $\beta_{y1} = 0.210$, so strengthening personality (X1) can improve the quality of instructor service (Y).

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- b. There is a significant positive direct effect between interpersonal communication (X2) on the quality of instructor service (Y) with $\beta_{y2} = 0.354$, so strengthening interpersonal communication (X2) can improve the quality of instructor service (Y).
- c. There is a significant positive direct effect between organizational support (X3) on the quality of instructor service (Y) with $\beta_{y3} = 0.173$ so strengthening organizational support (X3) can improve the quality of instructor service (Y).
- d. There is a significant positive direct effect between job satisfaction (X4) on the quality of instructor service (Y) with $\beta_{y4} = 0.194$, so strengthening job satisfaction (X4) can improve the quality of instructor service (Y).
- e. There is a significant positive direct effect between personality (X1) on job satisfaction (X4) with $\beta_{x1x4} = 0.236$ so strengthening personality (X1) can increase job satisfaction (X4).
- f. There is a significant positive direct effect between interpersonal communication (X2) on job satisfaction (X4) with $\beta_{x2x4} = 0.238$ so strengthening interpersonal communication (X2) can increase job satisfaction (X4).
- g. There is a significant positive direct effect between organizational support (X3) on job satisfaction (X4) with $\beta_{x3x4} = 0.233$, so strengthening organizational support (X3) can increase job satisfaction (X4).
- h. There is a significant positive indirect effect between personality (X1) on instructor service quality (Y) through job satisfaction (X4) with $\beta_{14y} = 0.049$ so strengthening personality (X1) can increase instructor service quality (Y) through job satisfaction (X4). Job satisfaction (X4) cannot function effectively as an intervening variable between personality (X1) and instructor service quality (Y) because the direct influence is greater than the indirect influence.
- i. There is a significant positive indirect influence between interpersonal communication (X2) on instructor service quality (Y) through job satisfaction (X4) with $\beta_{24y} = 0.084$ so strengthening interpersonal communication (X2) can improve instructor service quality (Y) through job satisfaction (X4). However, job satisfaction (X4) cannot function effectively as an intervening variable between interpersonal communication (X2) and instructor service quality (Y) because the direct influence is greater than the indirect influence.
- j. There is a significant positive indirect influence between organizational support (X3) on instructor service quality (Y) through job satisfaction (X4) with $\beta_{34y} = 0.040$ so strengthening organizational support (X3) can improve instructor service quality (Y) through job satisfaction (X4). However, job satisfaction (X4) cannot function effectively as an intervening variable between organizational support (X3) and instructor service quality (Y) because the direct influence is greater than the indirect influence.

IMPLICATIONS

Based on the conclusions above, the implications of this study are as follows:

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1. If the quality of instructor services is to be improved, it is necessary to strengthen personality, interpersonal communication, and organizational support as exogenous variables with job satisfaction as an intervening variable.
2. If personality is to be strengthened, it is done by improving indicators that are still weak, namely: conscientiousness and generosity (agreeableness). Maintaining or developing indicators, namely: emotional stability, openness to social interaction (extraversion), and openness to new experiences.
3. If interpersonal communication is to be strengthened, it is done by improving indicators that are still weak, namely: providing views, ideas, and concepts for the advancement of the organization. Maintaining or developing indicators, namely: openness to receive input from others, being positive towards yourself and others, ability to interpret every word, sentence, information, and behavior of others, ability to understand others, and providing support to others.
4. If organizational support is to be strengthened, then it is done by improving the indicators that are still weak, namely: job conditions, supervisor support, and organizational rewards. Maintaining or developing indicators, namely: fairness.
5. If job satisfaction is to be strengthened, then it is done by improving the indicators that are still weak, namely: promotion opportunities, 2) co-workers, and job conditions. Maintaining or developing indicators, namely: rewards (pay) and supervisor supervision.

SUGGESTION

Based on the explanation above, there are several strategies that can be used to improve the quality of instructor services. The instructor service quality strategies are strengthening personality variables, interpersonal communication, organizational support, and job satisfaction. The way to improve the quality of instructor services is to make improvements to indicators that are still low and maintain or develop indicators that are already good. The following are efforts that can be made to improve indicators that are still low and maintain or improve indicators That are already good. Implementation of each suggestion is based on the results of the SITOREM analysis by considering the capabilities of organizational resources at the CIMB Niaga Jakarta Employee Training Institute.

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